

An Archaeology of Catastrophe and Resilience in Aegean Thrace: Environmental Risks and Human-Inflicted Hazards

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Abstract: The increase in recent years of studies stressing the impacts of natural disasters, pandemics or conflicts on ancient societies indicates the significant effect that these had on cultural histories. Thus, the ability of ancient societies to adapt successfully to catastrophic features of their natural and man-made environment in a sustainable fashion becomes elementary in any attempt to understand change and development. The south part of ancient Thrace, the main passage towards the East, had its own shares of catastrophes either these were natural events or human-made destructions. Floods, pandemics, earthquakes, conflicts are beginning to be recognized as key factors within the process of cultural evolution and in the shaping of the environment. The overall aim of this article is to critically examine the role (direct or indirect) of extreme catastrophic events (natural processes or results of conflicts) in the area of Aegean Thrace in causing change, reaction, contraction in the settlement strategy of the area during the Imperial period.

Key words: catastrophe, destruction, environment, conflict, resilience.

INTRODUCTION: CATASTROPHE, DESTRUCTION AND RESILIENCE

Catastrophe and destruction, either natural or caused by human agency (conflicts – raids) is a basic parameter of the development of human habitus. Disasters and risks have substantial social and psychological impact (Ungar 2011), which reflect not only the impact characteristics such as the magnitude and severity, but also the pre-existing social and economic vulnerabilities (Torrence / Grattan 2002). The increase in recent years of studies stressing the impacts of disasters and hazards on ancient societies indicates the significant effect that these have on understanding cultural histories (Laoupi 2016; Gould 2007). Over the years, different definitions have been put forward about what a disaster is, but they all seem to converge that the critical and, quite often, quantitative element of a disaster is the human group itself, its habitat and the decision strategies that this group makes after the event (Torrence / Grattan 2002, 5-7).

More recently, resilience and persistence are also beginning to be recognized as key factors within the process (Bottrell 2009). Resilience can have varying conceptualizations in different contexts and disciplines (Middleton 2017) but it is increasingly used to frame research in archaeology as a term related to the capacity of a system to absorb the shock and to sustain and develop its fundamental function, structure, identity, through recovery or reorganization in a new context. The em-

ployment of the term as a means to describe the process of reactions against extreme catastrophic events (Ungar 2011) appears to be extremely intriguing because it implies a conscious act, that of a positive reaction, which can allow us to view the archaeology of an area under a new scope and therefore phrase a totally new set of questions or address new issues – questions such as:

To what extent did severe events have a significant effect on habitation and settlement patterns? What role did these dangers play in short- and long-term settlement strategies? What were the potential effects of the different hazards on human responses?

Responding to the call of the editors to reflect on catastrophe and conflict, this paper aims to explore the impact of natural and man-inflicted hazards on landscapes and settlement organization during the Imperial period in the area of Aegean Thrace (Loukopoulou 2004). The geomorphology of the area (Yassoglou et al. 2017, 71-85; Tsiafakis / Evangelidis 2021) and its character as the main passage towards the East (Lolos 2007), assured that the different groups of people living here (**fig. 1**) experienced their own share of hazards and catastrophes, natural or man-made. Given the different ethno-cultural contexts that coexisted in the area (Baralis 2008; for the Imperial period, see Evangelidis 2020), this is a field of study that presents challenges in interpretation unprecedented in Greek archaeology. One of these challenges is for instance to describe how the different groups living in the area reacted to natural hazards or destructive events. Given the importance of exploring how hazards are spatially distributed within different regions in the Roman world, including Roman Thrace, this article hopes to provide a first step for better understanding of the nature and scale of residents' vulnerability and reaction to natural and anthropogenic risks.

THE ENVIRONMENTAL FACTOR: FLOODS AND DISEASES

Natural hazards and disasters like volcanic eruptions or extreme seismic events were experienced by ancient societies with the same shock, awe and fear that we experience them today (Stiros / Jones 1996). Despite the fact that the area of Aegean Thrace is considered, for the Greek seismic standards, as a rather stable seismic region (despite the existence of an active trench between Maroneia and Makri), several major (magnitude 6 plus) and numerous minor earthquakes have occurred in the area (especially during the clustering of earthquakes during the 4th – 6th centuries AD known to geologists as the “*Early Byzantine Tectonic Paroxysm*”, see Pirazzoli 1986), but as usual the generic descriptions in the sources cannot help us extract specific evidence about the level and the nature of destruction (on seismic events in Thrace, see Ambraseys 2009, 89, 172-178, 197-198, 208-211).

Despite the dramatic character in loss of life and destruction that an earthquake quite often has, the influence of the natural hazards in our case can be best illustrated by the impact of floods and diseases. There is no doubt that the lowlands of the Rhodope was an alluvial zone where wetlands and seasonally flooded landscapes (Gerakis et al. 2007) in combination to river activity had far reaching negative implications for local populations than earthquakes. Through frequent changes in river water capacity and avulsions the unique hydrology created a topography (**fig. 2**) favoring the formation of high water table and overflows (Xeidakis et al. 2010, 1075).

Fig. 1. The area of Aegean Thrace: tribal groups and Greek cities (map: author)

Fig. 2. The geomorphology of the Deltaic plain of the Nestos and the Kosynthos rivers (map: author)

Fig. 3. Flash flood in the Kosynthos river (photo: author)

To this we should probably add frequently occurring severe flash flood incidents caused by intense rainfall in a short time (Koutsoyiannis et al. 2012). In contrast to Central European landscapes, the drainage network of the area is consisted by mountain torrents and small to medium size drainage basins with limited amount of discharge for most of the year (Skoulikidis et al. 2009), thus making flash flooding a very common type of danger (fig. 3). The damage from these rapidly rising, fast-moving waters of a flash flood can be devastating as recent events (a severe flash flood caused major damage in the city of Xanthi during the 1990s) have proved. Most importantly, floods and standing water by overflow of rivers can act as breeding sites for mosquitoes, and therefore enhance the potential for exposure of the population to infections such as different vectors of malaria, tertian fever and gastrointestinal illnesses (Manguin 2013; Sallares 2002). The ancient sources like Hippocrates (*Epid.* 1.2) indicate a strong presence of the most dangerous strains of malaria like *P. Falciparum* (Sallares 2002; Sallares et al. 2004) with symptoms like tertian fever which is typical of falciparian infections. The effects of malaria which was endemic in the area till the mid-20th century are characteristic (Λιβαδάς 1955): high mortality rates, anemia and jaundice, muscle fatigue and weakness. Even the least deadly string of malaria entails a series of recur-

ring episodes of chills, intense fever, and sweating and often includes other symptoms such as headache, fatigue, body aches, nausea, and vomiting.

These were exactly the kinds of hazards that could have had long-term effects in the livelihoods of the local groups who settled along the foot of the Rhodope (Tsiafakis / Evangelidis 2021). Sites close to the floodplain involved elements at risk such as the residents themselves, the built environment and the agro-pastoral economy. The understanding of these natural hazards by the people living in the area may have contributed to effective decision-making about settlement. In response to a series of flooding and drainage incidents the people could have decided in the best settlement location and adapted their subsistence strategies. These included a preference to mountainous or semi-mountainous sites or even a seasonal pattern of habitation (appropriate for seasonal diseases). The extensive occupation zone (of almost 31 square km) that lay at the area between the modern villages of Kimmeria, Lefkopetra – Akarpo, Filia and Vafeika is a case in point (fig. 4). A number of sites dating from the Late Hellenistic to the Late Roman period (with recorded previous phases) have been investigated on the lowlands of the foot of the Rhodope range (Evangelidis 2021, 503-507), away from floods, mosquito zones and alluvial soil. Clusters of houses (Lefkopetra), tumuli (in the case of Kimmeria), kilns (Vafeika), burials (Vafeika) and great concentrations of pottery (Akarpo) indicate the existence of a dispersed pattern of evenly spaced sites that might reflect settlements with an amazing longevity from Early Hellenistic to Late Roman times and the Byzantine period. In the cases of Kimmeria, Lefkopetra and Filia the settlements were developed at the foot of the Rhodope range and the beginning (or the ending) of important mountain trails leading to the interior, towards the Echinus Junction and from there to Bulgaria. The importance of these trails was emphasized more with the presence of forts (Kimmeria, Lefkopetra – Zarkadia and Filia), the sites of which seem to have been occupied for centuries. The pattern of a mountainous fort, trail and dispersed rural sites at its foot may have had an important role in indigenous spatial organization and it appears in other sites along the foot of the Rhodope range.

This settlement pattern, the manifestation of their ability to cope with floods which mostly arise fairly rapidly and endemic diseases, does not seem to change radically in Roman times. As in previous periods it seems that no strategies enabling large scale agricultural exploitation were employed and few installations of villa type or large estates have been found in the floodplain (Evangelidis 2021, 509). Therefore, instead of a rational Romanized landscape characterized by villas and organized agricultural activities in a controlled floodplain (an idea that seems to predominate in the archaeological literature), this was a landscape dotted by features that they speak of the continued importance of traditional settlement strategies. This was a landscape with distinctive characteristics identifying it from an environmental perspective: good drainage and avoidance of low-lying areas.

The magnitude and scale of natural damage were not only influenced by the hazard's characteristics but also by the vulnerability and exposure of the people that lived in the particular physical environment. A key factor in understanding the role of a catastrophic

Fig. 4. Distribution of settlements, remains and fortified enclosures of the Roman period in the area of Xanthi (map: author)

event is therefore resilience and persistence. Discussing about resilience, the case of Abdera needs to be stressed out (Isaac 1997, 73-108; Loukopoulou 2004, 872-875). The coastal promontory between alluvial plains where the Greek city developed is characterized by an extensive wetland prone to floods and endemic diseases (Agelarakis 2009-2010, 193). Environmental hazards were not unknown in the area and during the long history of the city the Abderitans had to fight against two very destructive hazards: floods and diseases. We can only imagine that the struggle to control the neighboring marshes and the infectious diseases that these would have nourished would have been constant for the city. Although it is not always easy to track variation in the mortality rate across the period, the osteopathological research of N. Agelarakis has highlighted the extensive presence of malaria from the early Archaic colonization to the Middle ages (Agelarakis 2009-2010, 194).

All things considered, despite the severity of the hazards, they did not lead to abandonment. On the contrary, as in other malaria-stricken places, the environmental risks were continually weighed and possibly socially controlled. These annually expected fevers were a familiar risk that the inhabitants of Abdera seem to have chosen to fight (a kind of positive response against catastrophe). Recent studies have shown that clear perception of the risks can help with the process of successful dealing with a catastrophe or its aftermath (Ungar 2011, 11). Thus, communities had time to consider a number of settlement strategies. In this case, persistence of habitation led eventually to naturally developed mutations (thalassemia, sickle cell trait and G6PD deficiency) against long-standing diseases. Individuals that carried the sickle cell trait or the G6PD deficiency (Sallares et al. 2004, 325) were in fact highly protected against malaria, thus explaining the high prevalence of this mutation in geographical areas where malaria is endemic (Penman et al. 2012). As noticed by Sallares (Sallares et al. 2004, 315, note 21), by the 5th c. BC at least some populations in North Greece (and among them probably the inhabitants of Abdera) already had a high frequency in such genetic mutations conferring some resistance to malaria.

The Greeks in the coast and their descendants down to the Late Roman times appear to be willing to take quite high risks in order to

reap the long-term benefits of the location such as trade and access to inland roads. In Abdera, the long-term benefit of locating a settlement in the particular place with the luxury of a safe harbor (Loukopoulou 2004, 871; Samiou 1999; Agelarakis 2009-2010, 197; Isaac 1987, 74, note 15) or the lack of suitable alternatives appear to override any concern relating to rare, if catastrophic, environmental events or diseases which occurred frequently over a long period. Alternative explanations as attachment to land may also explain the risk taken.

The end of the classical city of Abdera was marked by a great flood in the 4th c. AD, traces of which have been detected around the west gate (Κουκούλη-Χρυσανθάκη 1988, 58). This has been regarded as the last of a series of catastrophic environmental events that eventually led the Abderitans to abandon the site and move to a higher ground at the site of the Byzantine Polystylon. The silting of the west gate of Abdera though indicates in my opinion not so much a sudden environmental catastrophe but foremost the inability of the community to face with adequate resources the long-standing dangers against whom the Abderitans were fighting since the time of the first settlement. What seems to change over the years is the level of community's resilience and vulnerability against the anthropogenic and environmental hazards that endangered the fate of the city throughout Antiquity. To lose resilience in this case, was to become prone to collapse (Middleton 2017, 43). It is worth noting that despite the risky environment and the occasional catastrophes, the fluvial and estuarine data suggest the presence – throughout the historical period – of a stable ecosystem that was constantly controlled (probably at a great cost) by the city. Therefore, the site's abandonment and loss of features associated with urbanism seem to be linked more to broader changes (Evangelidis 2021, 512) that were not principally reliant on natural hazards rather than to a sudden environmental natural catastrophic event such as the flood that silted the west gate of the city.

CONFLICT AND WARFARE: THE IMPRINT ON THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL RECORD

Identifying warfare and conflict in the material record is a difficult task and it is often plagued by the incomplete nature of archaeological evidence, mostly defensive structures, evidence for destruction (like atypical burials or destroyed buildings) and weapons (or objects that can be used as weapons). Using evidence as such to explore the nature of conflict (Otto 2006, 25) is not without methodological problems and indicators like forts or weapons can quite often have alternative interpretations not necessarily bound with war or conflict (see the discussion in Randsborg 1995; Jørgensen 1999; Wileman 2009).

A number of sites in the area (many of them continuing well into the Imperial period) can be described as defensive in nature (Τριαντάφυλλος 1990), but these as shown by Efstratiou (Ευστρατίου 1988) can be a product of our interpretation and not the evidence itself. Some of them present no evidence of occupation and others are too far from settlements or roads. Walls made from dry stone such as the enceinte at the site Tsouka (near the village of Gorgona) or the small enceinte near Thamna (Τριαντάφυλλος 1978, 309-310) can be associated with diachronically pastoral activities suggesting an eco-

nomical rather than a defensive function. This of course does not exclude the possibility that many of them had been used as last resort refuges that could have served the needs of family or clans of unfortified settlements within a given district in time of crisis. Despite their rough construction these sites were perfectly defensible. Similarly, the fact that the Imperial period was characterized by low conflict level does not mean that strife between different clans or groups was nonexistent (Riess / Fagan 2016, 1-16); on the contrary, local conflicts could be significant drivers of violence. The principal problem relates to the definition of conflict which is largely based upon recorded instances of battles or invasions. These clearly account only for a fraction of ancient violence. Therefore, when discussing about warfare in Antiquity, we should probably consider other possibilities like blood feuds, livestock raids, robbery, duels in which the people of the area would need weapons or defenses.

On the other hand, the existence (and renovation) of permanent forts like the fort of Kalyva (Τριαντάφυλλος 1991) or the Roman fort at Kimmeria (Τριαντάφυλλος 1973-1974, 808) indicates that the need for centralized control over defense was never out of the question. Although a first reading of the evidence suggests a tangible relationship between defense and the need for defense, it is difficult not to see the existence of a circular argument. Equally circular is the logic that sees the varied weapon combinations and skeletal remains of horses discovered in furnished burials in the area as direct reflections of a warlike society, in which status and power were entangled with violence and conflict (Τερζοπούλου 2013, 338, with bibliography). Weapons (swords, lances, knives and occasionally shield bosses) and remains of horses have been discovered in different tumuli burials like in Thyrea, Orestiada, Rhegion, Kyane and Lade. All have been interpreted as items of symbolic importance in a culture that appraised military warrior values (Τερζοπούλου 2013, 99-100; Τριαντάφυλλος / Τερζοπούλου 1996).

Interestingly though, as in other similar contexts across Europe (for instance in Germany or Gaul, see Ebel 1998), weapon burials seem to peak during a period of peace, when one might expect to find fewer “warrior” burials. Therefore, it is likely that all these grave goods had many more connotations besides warfare. It is possible that the act of horse burial or the laying of weapons performed a specific communicative function (during the pre-burial rites) which served to proclaim and strengthen particular identities associations within Imperial period Thrace (Evangelidis 2020, 54).

Another major problem is the inability to successfully correlate archaeological evidence with events mentioned in the ancient sources. As noticed by P. Delev (Делев 2014, 4), the reliability of these sources and the exaggeration of description present limitations to the interpretation of archaeological data. In some instances, the losses of population appear to have been less severe than those described by the literary sources while in most of the cases the city was not abandoned after the event. The Slavic attack of AD 549 on Topeiros is illustrative for such literary *topoi* (Agelarakis 2020, 33-35).

“Then they slew all the men immediately, to the number of fifteen thousand, took all the valuables as plunder, and reduced the children and women to slavery. Before this, however, they had spared no age...

had been killing all who fell in their way, young and old alike, so that the whole land inhabited by the Illyrians and Thracians came to be everywhere filled with unburied corpses" (Procop. *Goth.*7.38.18-23)¹.

Similar stories about invading armies have been passed down in oral and written history but the real effect of such acts of war is difficult to be evaluated. The imagery of human-caused devastation has an important role in the theorization of urban decline but whether a sudden anthropogenic act of war can have a really destructive effect depends very much on the interpretation we give. While the influence of an act of war is a factor that may be hazardous (buildings with signs of damage and destruction deposits bear witness of significant disasters), few such events have been responsible for sudden decline, as is the case with the destruction of Olynthus by Philip II (see Cawkwell 1962).

Abdera once more is a case in point. The confiscation of 50.000 *modii* of wheat from Abdera by the consul L. Hortensius and the storm (and destruction) of the city is a well recorded incident of the Third Macedonian War (Diod. 30.6; Liv. 43.4.8) which has quite often been mentioned as the starting point for the decline of the city during the subsequent period (Kallintzi 2018, 21; *contra* Papaioannou 2010, 54). Although Roman savagery and overt violence was not unusual during the Republican period (it has to be noted that it was normal for the generals of the period to requisition supplies on a large scale), a vicious attack on a Greek allied city took destruction on a total different level. Providing supplies for a Roman army was a tremendous task and the confiscation of almost forty tons of wheat must have been a serious blow on local economy, but we may wonder: Was it enough to drive the economy of Abdera to destruction and lead the city to permanent state of decline?

What archaeological and epigraphical evidence (Papaioannou 2010, 60, note 51; *IThrAeg* 166) has shown us is that despite the severity of the impact and the image of destruction drawn by the ancient sources, the early Imperial period at Abdera was marked by financial activity, the presence of Roman *negotiatores*, the minting of bronze coins and building activity with new habitation quarters and artisanal areas towards the sea (Chrysanthaki 2004, 317). Cities such as Abdera have geographical advantages which do not die easily by an economic blow. The city held a position not only central to this part of Aegean Thrace, but also to the North Aegean Sea and land routes. As long as these advantages were not wiped out by some extreme natural or human action (such as a radical change in the course of the river or the total destruction of the city), the city could, and did, derive continuing benefit from them, throughout the Imperial period.

Thus, the "decline" is best discussed in terms of the broader transformations in the political landscape (e.g. the rise and the aggressive policies of the Thracian client kingdom) of the region during the Late Republican and Early Imperial period (Evangelidis 2021, 512) rather than the result of a single event. As the period wore on, other pressures such as the emergence of the new urban centers (like Topeiros) and the general destabilization of the area in Late Antiquity under the pressure of barbaric raids conspired against the growth of the city. When the city entered the Early Christian period, its long and successful policies ended; it underwent economic change and population loss which led to urban shrinkage.

¹ Translation by H. B. Dewing (see Dewing 2014, 456)

CONCLUSIONS: STEPS TOWARDS AN ARCHAEOLOGY OF DESTRUCTION AND RESILIENCE

One of the most valuable lessons to be learned from considering urban and rural histories from the perspective of conflict and destruction is that we must be willing to consider long-term cycles (long-term developments) and a greater range of effects than what a single destructive event implies. It is also worth pointing that drastic change or collapse is not necessarily an aftermath of destruction (Middleton 2017, 46-48) and there are in any case many factors that could account for resilience.

Nonetheless, the question of how archaeology can identify and assess environmental and human-inflicted destruction (beyond obvious cases like *Pompeii* or *Olynthus*) remains a crucial but problematic one (see the discussion in Torrence / Grattan 2002, 8-11; Middleton 2017, 43). A major difficulty is that not all catastrophic events can create archaeologically detectable evidence. The limitation or, quite often, the absence of archaeological evidence has clearly an effect on the way we understand destruction. Thus, analyzing patterns of destruction and conflict requires extensive data (especially bioarchaeological and mortuary data which can give some more concise answers) combined with text and chronological framework.

The task is becoming more difficult when the discussion comes to the Imperial period, a significant period of peace, low conflict and climatic stability. In the absence of major catastrophic natural events (at least in the area under discussion), the focus of research can be turned on the ways that people dealt with existing hazards. Floods, drainage problems and endemic diseases for instance – besides their direct effects – can be, as we have seen, a catalyst for long-term habitation patterns. The wetter conditions suggested by climate reconstructions for between circa 100 BC and AD 200 (McCormick et al. 2012) would have exacerbated the risky environment through storm events, drainage problems in the low-lying areas and spread of vector diseases. Within this environment – and as in many other pre-industrial societies – environmental constraints, hazards and sudden shocks were part of a constant interaction, which kept local societies trapped at a specific form of economy and habitation habit, by dictating their resource base.

What it would be interesting to examine is whether the technology and engineering of the Imperial period (for instance, dredging or canal construction) helped to withstand against long-standing dangers or how environmental knowledge and reaction was changed and by whom. Evidence, though, for successful management like construction of dams or dredging in the area is minimal. On the contrary, the archaeological evidence suggests that reaction was adjusted to the level of the local experience rather than to the available engineering knowhow. This implies that the communities living in the area assessed risks in different ways and different strategies were employed in response to different types of forcing mechanisms. In the case of the communities of Thracians living at the foot of the Rhodope range for instance, their persistence on traditional settlement strategy and economic modes (pastoralism and mixed farming) enabled them to avoid the risk-laden environment of the deltaic plain. Areas proximal to floodplain were utilized mostly for pastoral activities while settlements continued to be rooted in the mountainous areas. In the case of Abdera, long-term strategies and persistence of habitation despite the

severity of dangers were critical to the way people and central authority responded to the management of wetlands. In both cases this was the outcome of living in a risky environment. Nonetheless, urbanization like the development of *Torpeiros* (Λουκοπούλου 1989; *IThrAeg* 261-265) into a substantial settlement – city and the construction of the road network, a project that involved the construction of *via Egnatia* (Lolos 2007; Lolos 2008 with full bibliography) and the upgrade of secondary roads, could have been a trigger for better management of this marginal area. After all, inhabitation and exploitation of the alluvial plain that surrounds the city would not have been possible without successful strategies and investments in infrastructure.

Historical reasoning about the impact of disasters is colored by *Pompeii*-style single events or total acts of war; stories of collapse which are ideal for their romantic and tragic appeal. While these cases can be useful in their particular contexts, a more flexible approach to the issue of the impact of a hazard/disaster would have considered a wider framework of parameters, like the relationship between natural processes such as flood or alluviation and cultural responses. The same can be said about conflict. Although connotations of sieges, warfare and armies are difficult to be avoided, the analysis of regional pattern of conflict needs to take into account a wider range of evidence and alternative explanations, which focus on economy and site hierarchy. Given the fact that environmental knowledge is socially dynamic (Walsh et al. 2014, 28), what needs to be explored further is if (and how) the difference in the reactions between the different areas of the region under study in case of danger might match diverging relationships between different groups of people.

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